

A STUDY OF THE IMPACT AND REFLECTION OF VISION AND MISSION STATEMENT ON ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE OF SELECTED ENGLISH MEDIUM COLLEGES OF TEACHER EDUCATION AFFILIATED TO THE UNIVERSITY OF MUMBAI

Elvina Pereira

St.Xavier's Institute of Education,Mumbai

INTRODUCTION

India's education system is facing challenges that may be one of the biggest facing any nation in the 21st Century. Especially higher education in modern Indian society seeks to preserve, transmit and advance knowledge. Many experts, committees and commissions have underlined the importance of education as an instrument of change and progress. The task of nation building depends on the quality and number of persons coming out of our schools and colleges.

RATIONALE FOR THE STUDY

Today well-managed corporate entities have become the dominant productive vehicle in society. This raises a profound question on the responsibility of the educational institutions in the 21st century.

The vision and the mission of an organization emerge from important social, economic, spiritual and political values. They are meant to inspire and promote organizational loyalty. Vision and mission are those parts of an organization that appeal to the heart; that is, they represent the organization's emotional appeal. They motivate people and draw upon staff and stakeholders' hopes and aspirations. In this sense, the vision and mission of an organization provide inspirational motivation. The researcher having been in the field of teacher education for almost a decade believes that vision and mission statement of educational institutions play very vital role in the image building of every institution. Therefore it is imperative that the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement be studied with great importance.

NEED OF THE STUDY

To the best of researcher's knowledge in the past very few researches have been conducted on vision and mission statement of the educational institutions in India and almost none when it comes to colleges of teacher education in India.

The present research focuses on impact and reflection of vision and mission statement of colleges of education on the behaviour of teacher educators and student teachers with respect to: academic excellence

STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

A Study of the Impact and Reflection of Vision and Mission Statement on Academic Excellence of Selected English Medium Colleges of Teacher Education Affiliated to the University of Mumbai

DEFINITIONS OF THE VARIABLES

IMPACT AND REFLECTION

For the present study impact and reflection has been defined as the perception of student teachers and teacher educators on the overall and specific behaviour of the selected colleges of teacher education

VISION STATEMENT

According to business dictionary, “An aspirational description of what an organization would like to achieve or accomplish in the mid-term or long-term future.

It is intended to serves as a clear guide for choosing current and future courses of action.”

MISSION STATEMENT

According to business dictionary, “A written declaration of an organization's core purpose and focus that normally remains unchanged over time. Properly crafted mission statements (1) serve as filters to separate what is important from what is not, (2) clearly state which markets will be served and how, and (3) communicate a sense of intended direction to the entire organization.”

VISION AND MISSION STATEMENT

For the present study vision and mission statement has been defined as the philosophy of the managements of selected English medium colleges of teacher education which projects where the institution should go and what major changes and challenges it should adopt and how to link its activities to the needs of the society and legitimize its existence

Academic Excellence

The impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators were studied with respect to following areas which were further divided into aspects:

1. Academic Excellence

- a) Academic planning
- b) Teaching strategies
- c) Teacher qualities

DEFINITIONS OF AREAS STUDIED

In the following areas the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators are studied aspect wise as follows:

ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE

For the present study academic excellence is defined as how selected colleges of teacher education has an impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the overall and specific behaviour of their student teachers and teacher educators in order to utilize their intellectual capacity, ability to perform, achieve, and/or excel in scholastic activities. The aspects highlights that academic excellence is not just achieving high grades and showing superior performance but it is the maximum development of intellectual capacities and skills through academic planning, teaching strategies and teacher qualities.

AIMS OF THE STUDY

The aims of the present study are:

1. To study the impact and reflection of the vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators in the area of Academic Excellence of selected colleges of teacher education in the area of Academic Excellence

Objectives of the study

1. To study the impact and reflection of the vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators in the area of Academic Excellence of selected colleges of teacher education affiliated to the University of Mumbai

SCOPE AND DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present research study includes the impact and reflection of the vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators of selected colleges of teacher education affiliated to the University of Mumbai with respect to Academic Excellence

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Researcher is well aware that the area of present research is extremely challenging, very complex and vast and hence to bring out all the dimensions of vision and mission statement is very difficult. The attempt made by the researcher may not be very profound and the approach also might look too simple for such a complex area. For the present study only English Medium colleges of teacher education were selected within the geographical boundaries of greater Mumbai. Present study includes equal number of aided and unaided colleges of teacher education. While selecting the colleges of teacher education two criteria were kept in mind NAAC accredited and more than five years of existence. Hence only those colleges of teacher education were selected for the study.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Researcher personally believes that in the current situation of rapid change only those teacher education institutions will be able to survive and excel which are flexible, adaptive and productive. For this to happen it is important for all the teacher education institutions to have genuine vision and mission statement which they are able to communicate easily and frequently not only internally but also to the external world.

BRIEF THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE AREA

ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE

Academic excellence is the demonstrated ability to perform, achieve, and/or excel in scholastic activities. Academic excellence has been identified with achieving high grades and superior performance. But academic excellence is more than just making good grades. It is the maximum development of one's intellectual capacities and skills in service to humanity. Excellence connotes the quality of being very good, distinguished and outstanding.

The changing scenario in teacher education with ICT and global job market for teaching opportunities the ongoing efforts to improve the quality of teacher education should develop an ability in both the student teachers and the teacher educators to apply what they learned in the colleges of teacher education to a variety of ever-changing situations that they couldn't foresee. This is the real mark of a quality teacher education and a truer indication of academic excellence in teacher education.

While achieving this quality and excellence teacher education institutions need to implement this transformation through their vision and mission statements where the focus will be more on behaviour rather than simply talk about. Hence if teacher education institutions want to be outstanding and distinguished then they need to have very clearly communicated vision and mission statement.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present research study aimed at impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators of selected English medium colleges of teacher education. There were many areas and aspects which are compared. Hence the descriptive method of comparative type was adopted to compare the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the overall and specific behaviour in the areas in the categories. A descriptive, comparative research design was used to compare the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the area of academic excellence.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population of present research study consists of student teachers and teacher educators of aided and unaided colleges of teacher education in the Greater Mumbai area.

SAMPLING

The B.Ed colleges of teacher education in Greater Mumbai are mainly of two types, aided and unaided. The researcher identified the colleges that are completed minimum 5 years of existence and atleast once gone through NAAC accreditation. The sample of the study was selected using purposive sampling method.

NATURE AND SIZE OF THE SAMPLE

The sample of the present study consists of 570 student teachers studying in selected English medium aided and unaided colleges of teacher education affiliated to the University of Mumbai, situated in Greater Mumbai area, minimum 5 years of existence and atleast once gone through NAAC accreditation.

The sample of the present study also consists of 78 teacher educators teaching in selected English medium colleges of teacher education affiliated to the University of Mumbai, situated in Greater Mumbai area, minimum 5 years of existence and at least once gone through NAAC accreditation.

PREPARATION OF THE TOOLS

For the present research studies following tools were prepared by the researcher.

1. Personal data sheet for the student teachers.
2. Personal data sheet for the teacher educators.

3. Academic excellence rating scale

This rating scale was prepared by the researcher to study the opinion of the student teachers and teacher educators about the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on academic excellence. It is a five-point rating scale and contains 24 items.

DATA COLLECTION

Almost all the selected teacher education colleges cooperated and researcher got the permission to collect data.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

In this stage the tabulated data are scientifically and systematically studied in order to determine underlying, inherent facts or relationships.

Tabulation refers to the recording of the classified scores. The present study required the data collected from student teachers to be tabulated in the categories of type of institution of teacher education that is aided and unaided, gender wise composition of the student teachers and on the basis of qualifications.

The data collected from the teacher educators to be tabulated in the categories of type of institution of teacher education that is aided and unaided, qualification wise that is only M.Ed and M.Ed with Ph.D and /or M.Phil and on the basis of teaching experience from 0-12 years and 13 years and above.

In the present study, two types of analyses are adopted

1. Descriptive Analysis

Figure 1.1

Descriptive statistics of scores of impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of Academic Excellence of selected colleges of teacher education

Area	Categories	N	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
AE	Total	570	100.09	102.00	112.00	12.42	-.939	.950
Type	Aided	330	101.44	104.00	112.00	11.89	-.871	.134
	Unaided	240	98.23	100.00	98.00	12.91	-.994	1.406
Gender	Male	47	96.06	97.00	102.00	11.44	-.073	0.48
	Female	523	100.45	103.00	112.00	12.45	-1.023	1.186
Quali	Grad	397	99.30	101.00	112.00	12.82	-.921	.833
	Post Grad	173	101.90	104.00	105.00	11.28	-.906	1.052

The descriptive statistics for the academic excellence scores for student teachers of colleges of teacher education are presented in table 5.14. The mean and the median values for the total sample and for the categories do not differ much, which indicates normality of the distribution. The S.D. for all the distributions is almost the same. All the distributions are slightly negatively skewed showing high academic excellence in the total sample as well as the categories. The kurtosis values indicate that the

distributions are platykurtic in nature in most of the categories except in the category of aided colleges of education which is leptokurtic or peaked in nature. This indicates high concentration of scores at the higher end.

The original and the smoothed frequency polygons depict the distributions in a pictorial form and support the distribution of the descriptive statistics

Figure 1.2 Overall Student Teachers

The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of academic excellence of the colleges of teacher education almost align with each other and they also have the same rise and fall. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The curve indicates that the distribution is platykurtic in nature also the distribution is negatively skewed and it does not have normal shape. It also shows that maximum distribution lies on the extreme end of the X axis which shows very high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of the student teachers in the area of academic excellence of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.3 Student Teachers of Aided Colleges of Teacher Education

The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of academic excellence of aided colleges of teacher education almost align with each other and they also have the same rise and fall. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The curve indicates that the distribution is leptokurtic in nature also the distribution is negatively skewed. It also indicates that the maximum distribution lies on the extreme end of X axis which shows very high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of the student teachers in the area of academic excellence of selected aided colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.4 Student Teachers of Unaided Colleges of Teacher Education

The original and smoothed frequency Polygon for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of academic excellence of unaided colleges of education almost overlap with each other. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is leptokurtic in nature. The maximum distribution lies towards the extreme right which shows very high impact and reflection of vision and mission

statement on the specific behaviour of the student teachers in the area of academic excellence of selected aided colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.5 Male Student Teachers of Colleges of Teacher Education

The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of male student teachers in the area of academic excellence of colleges of teacher education differs. The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is leptokurtic in nature. The frequency polygon shows on peak which is at the centre indicating maximum distribution indicate normal impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of the male student teachers in the area of academic excellence of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.6 Female Student Teachers of Colleges of Teacher Education

The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of female student teachers in the area of academic excellence of colleges of teacher education almost aligns one another. The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is platykurtic in nature. The frequency polygon indicates one peak indicating maximum distribution lies to the extreme right of X axis which shows high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of the female student teachers in the area of academic excellence of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.7 Graduate Student Teachers of Colleges of Teacher Education

The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of graduate student teachers in the area of academic excellence of colleges of teacher education almost overlaps with each other. The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is platykurtic in nature. The frequency polygon indicates one peak showing maximum distribution lies towards the extreme right, which means high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of the graduate student

teachers in the area of academic excellence of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.8 Post- Graduate Student Teachers of Colleges of Teacher Education

The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of post graduate student teachers in the area of academic excellence of colleges of teacher education differ significantly. The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is platykurtic. The frequency polygon shows one peak which is very prominent indicates maximum distribution lies towards the extreme right indicating high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of the post graduate student teachers in the area of academic excellence of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.9

Descriptive statistics of scores of impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of academic excellence of selected colleges of teacher education

Area	Categories	N	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
AE	Total	78	94.55	96.00	93.00	14.64	-1.063	1.341
Types	Aided	44	94.43	99.00	111.00	16.55	-1.292	1.464
	Unaided	34	94.70	94.50	92.00	11.98	-.154	0.56
Quali	M.Ed with Ph.D and / or M.Phill	23	93.68	99.00	100.00	17.00	-1.246	1.725
	M.Ed	55	94.89	95.00	93.00	13.76	-.929	1.058
Tg.Exp.	0-12 yrs	50	101.56	104	116	12.99	-0.80	1.69
	13yrs&above	28	93.71	96.5	98	16.85	-1.19	1.69

The descriptive statistics for the academic excellence scores for teacher educators of colleges of teacher education are presented in table 5.16. The mean and the median values for the total sample and for the categories do not differ much except for the category of teaching experience between 0-12 years. Which indicates normality of the distributions. The S.D. for the total sample and for the teacher educators with M.Ed qualification is almost same. Whereas the S.D. for the aided colleges to teacher education, M.Ed with Ph.D, and/or M.Phil teacher educators and teacher educators with teaching experience 13 years and above is almost the same and the S.D. for unaided colleges of teacher education and teacher educators with teaching experience between 0-12 years is almost same. All the distributions are slightly negatively skewed showing high academic excellence in the total sample as well as the categories. The kurtosis values indicate that all the distributions are platykurtic in nature. This shows high concentration of scores at the higher end shows high concentration of scores at the higher end.

The original and the smoothed frequency polygons depict the distributions in a pictorial form and support the distribution of the descriptive statistics.

Figure 1.10 Overall Teacher Educators

The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of academic excellence of colleges of teacher education differ significantly.

The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is platykurtic. The frequency polygon shows one peak and it indicates maximum distribution lies on the extreme right showing high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of academic excellence of selected colleges of teacher education

Figure 1.11 Teacher Educators of Aided Colleges of Teacher Education

The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of academic excellence of aided colleges of education differ significantly.

The distribution is negatively skewed and it is platykurtic in nature. The frequency polygon indicates peak which shows maximum distribution lies towards the extreme right indicating high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of academic excellence of selected aided colleges of teacher education

Figure 1.12 Teacher Educators of Unaided Colleges of Teacher Education

The original and smoothed frequency polygon for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of academic excellence of unaided colleges of education differ significantly. The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is leptokurtic in nature. The frequency polygon indicates normal distribution showing maximum distribution lies at the centre indicating normal impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of academic excellence of selected unaided colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.13 Teacher Educators with Qualifications M.Ed with Ph.D, and / or M.Phil and only M.Ed.

From the bar diagram it is seen that the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the category of qualifications in the area of academic excellence of colleges of teacher education teacher educators with M.Ed with Ph.D and/or M.Phil qualifications is lesser than that of M.Ed qualifications.

Figure 1.14 Teacher Educators with Teaching Experience of 0-12 years and 13 and above

From the bar diagram it is seen that the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of academic excellence in the category of teaching experience of colleges of teacher education teacher educators with 0-12 years teaching experience is greater than that of teacher educators with teaching experience 13 years and above.

Major Findings

The impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of academic excellence does not differ significantly when compared in the categories of type of institution and qualifications of teacher educators. Whereas in the category of teaching experience teacher educators with the teaching experience 0-12 years show greater impact and reflection of vision and mission statement than teacher educators with the teaching experience 13 years and above.

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